

Use of Phenolic Acids in the Detection, Separation and Estimation of Metals. Part I.
A New Qualitative Method for the Separation of 2A Group (Analytical) Metals.

BY PABITRA NATH DAS-GUPTA.

The usual qualitative separation of 2A group metals is well known. In the proposed method the principle of separation of mercury from the rest of the metals is kept as usual and the new method is applied in the separation of lead, bismuth, copper and cadmium. The principles are based on the following facts :

(i) In dilute nitric acid solution gallic acid completely precipitates bismuth, whereas lead, copper and cadmium are unaffected, thus separating bismuth from the rest.

(ii) In neutral or faintly acid (nitric) solution gallic acid and sodium acetate completely precipitate lead and copper. Thus lead and copper are separated from cadmium.

(iii) In neutral or dilute nitric acid solution, hydrogen peroxide and ammonia completely precipitate lead (Das-Gupta, Roy and Sil, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 657), copper remaining in solution. This separates lead from copper.

When the question of precipitating the 2A group metals as sulphide does not arise, which is rarely the case, then, according to the new method, their separation is carried out by following the principles given below :—

(a) In dilute nitric acid solution of the metals, resorcylic acid completely precipitates mercury alone (separation of mercury from the rest).

(b) For the separation of bismuth, lead, copper and cadmium the principles mentioned in (i), (ii) and (iii) are followed.

In the existing method of separation, the rapidity of the process is greatly hampered in separating lead (as sulphate) from bismuth, copper and cadmium, whereas following the proposed method, the whole course of separation can be finished in much less time. Also

this method enables one to separate copper from cadmium. Further, the use of the poisonous chemical, potassium cyanide, is altogether avoided.

The action of three phenolic acids (tannic, gallic and resorcylic) on nitrates, chlorides, acetates and sulphates of the metals of 2A group has been thoroughly studied. It has been found that gallic and resorcylic acids are most suitable for the separation of the above metals. The nature of the precipitates obtained in the cases of mercury, bismuth, lead and copper by resorcylic acid, gallic acid and gallic acid + sodium acetate respectively, is under investigation. Further work on the separation and estimation of the metals of 2A group is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Solutions of the nitrates of mercury, bismuth, lead, copper and cadmium are prepared, of which the nitrate solutions of mercury and bismuth are acidic (due to free nitric acid required in the process of solution). In the solutions the amount of the respective metals present per c. c. is determined by the standard methods. With these solutions a study of the separation of 2A group metals is carried on as follows.

Action of Gallic Acid on Bismuth Nitrate Solution.

(1 c. c. = 0.0114 g. Bi; Free mineral acidity = $N/6$ nearly).

When a fresh 1% solution of gallic acid is added to the bismuth nitrate solution, at first a yellowish white bulky precipitate is formed: this, on warming, becomes crystalline (light yellow) and settles quickly. When a warm solution of bismuth nitrate is employed the precipitate readily becomes crystalline. But when both the reactants are hot, the light yellow crystalline precipitate is formed. The precipitate is insoluble in water, but soluble in dilute mineral acids or in excess of dilute acetic acid. On igniting the precipitate, organic matter is seen to burn and metallic bismuth is formed with the usual yellow oxide incrustation.

It has been found that gallic acid completely precipitates bismuth from the solution, when the concentration of acid (nitric) is $N/18$ or the total concentration of the acid after the addition of the reagent is $N/14$.

To prove this conclusively, the bismuth precipitate is treated with warm $N/10$ - and $N/14$ - nitric acids, with the result that the filtrate from $N/10$ -acid shows the presence of traces of bismuth only whereas the filtrate from $N/14$ -acid shows its complete absence. From the above, the conditions for the quantitative precipitation of bismuth from a solution of its nitrate stand as follows:—

(a) The solution should not contain more than free mineral (nitric) acidity of $N/18$.

(b) For each 0.1 g. bismuth present, the volume of the solution should not be less than 30 c. c.

It has also been observed that a suspension of bismuth hydroxide or bismuth oxynitrate reacts with warm gallic acid solution producing the usual light-yellow crystalline precipitate. In this connection it should be noted that for the precipitation of bismuth, the solution must be absolutely free from chloride, in the presence of which gallic acid produces practically no precipitate.

Action of Gallic Acid on Lead Nitrate Solution.

(1 c.c. = 0.02494 g. Pb).

When 1% gallic acid is added to lead acetate solution, an immediate white bulky precipitate with yellowish tinge is obtained, which on warming becomes crystalline and light yellow in colour and settles very quickly. But when lead nitrate solution is taken instead of the acetate, no precipitate is obtained, but on adding sodium acetate solution to this, a light yellow precipitate is obtained. This non-appearance of precipitate in lead nitrate solution is evidently due to the free nitric acid, liberated in the course of the reaction. It has been found that 1 c.c. of the lead nitrate solution, even when diluted to 100 times, produces no precipitate on the addition of the reagent. This behaviour helps the separation of bismuth from lead.

It has also been observed that gallic acid together with sodium acetate can effect a quantitative precipitation of lead from a warm and neutral solution of its nitrate provided that for each 0.025 g. of lead, the volume of the solution is not less than 15 c.c. In the case of acid (nitric) solution, quantitative precipitation can also be obtained provided that the free acidity is not more than $N/200$; for qualitative analysis free acidity of $N/100$ is quite satisfactory.

Experiments on the Quantitative Precipitation of Lead from its Nitrate Solution (Neutral or Acidic).

Neutral Solution.

Lead nitrate solution = 1 c.c. Sodium acetate (5%) = 2 c.c.

Expt.	Water c.c.	Gallic acid : 1% soln. c.c.	Total vol. c.c.	Dilution.	Liberated acidity calculated from the amount of Pb.	Remarks.
1	10	5	18	1/18	N/72	Lead almost absent.
2	15	5	23	1/23	N/92	Lead absent
3	15	2	20	1/20	N/80	"
4	20	5	28	1/28	N/112	"
5	25		33	1/33	N/132	"
6	10	3	16	1/16	N/64	Lead almost absent.
7	16	1	20	1/20	N/80	Much lead present.

Acid Solution.

Lead nitrate solution = 1 c.c. Sodium acetate (5%) = 3 c.c.
Gallic acid (1%) = 5 c.c. Total volume = 33 c.c.

Expt.	N/10. HNO ₃ c.c.	Water. c.c.	Free acidity.	Total acidity in the soln. after the reaction.	Remarks.
I	2.5	21.5	N/100	$\left(\frac{N}{10} \times \frac{2.5}{33} + \frac{N}{4} \times \frac{1}{33}\right) = \frac{N}{66}$	Lead almost absent.
II	1.25	22.75	N/200	$\left(\frac{N}{10} \times \frac{1.25}{33} + \frac{N}{4} \times \frac{1}{33}\right) = \frac{N}{88}$	Lead absent.
III	0.625	23.375	N/400	$\left(\frac{N}{10} \times \frac{0.625}{33} + \frac{N}{4} \times \frac{1}{33}\right) = \frac{N}{106}$	"

In all the experiments, sodium acetate is added gradually to the warm lead nitrate solution to which an excess of gallic acid has been added.

From Expts. 3 and 7 it is clear that for each 0.025 g. of lead at least 2 c.c. of 1% gallic acid should be used. In the case of acid solution, enough sodium acetate is added to produce a turbidity followed by 2 c.c. more.

The precipitate of lead, like that of bismuth, is insoluble in water and soluble in dilute acids. The solubility in mineral acids

is far greater than in acetic acid. Like the bismuth precipitate metallic lead is formed with yellow oxide incrustation on ignition.

Action of Gallic Acid on Copper Nitrate Solution.

(1 c.c. = 0.0239 g. Cu).

Gallic acid when added to a neutral solution of copper nitrate in the cold produces no change, but, when heated above 55°, the solution becomes turbid (brownish) and on boiling a part of the copper is thrown down as a chocolate-brown precipitate. If, however, the copper solution contains a little free nitric acid ($N/200$ or more) no change is produced even on boiling with gallic acid; with a concentration of $N/400$ -acid, a change in the colour of the solution is produced but no precipitation. With acetic acid, an acidity of $N/1$ or more can prevent the formation of the precipitate of copper. These observations make the separation of copper from bismuth possible. It should be noted, however, that as in the case of lead, copper can be precipitated completely from a solution of its nitrate by gallic acid and sodium acetate. In this case the precipitate is voluminous and is coloured chocolate-brown and takes longer time for settling.

For the complete precipitation of copper by gallic acid and sodium acetate, it is found that, in the copper nitrate solution, having free mineral acidity of $N/14$ after the addition of just excess gallic acid, an excess of sodium acetate can quantitatively precipitate 0.024g. of copper present in a volume of 25 c.c. In this case at least 4 c.c. of 1% gallic acid are required for 0.024 g. of copper. In this connection it should be noted that when both lead and copper are present in a solution, for the complete precipitation of lead with copper, the solution should be so diluted that the resultant acidity (acetic) will not be more than $N/66$.

The precipitate of copper, on ignition, leaves black cupric oxide. It is insoluble in water.

Action of Gallic Acid on Cadmium Nitrate Solution

(1 c.c. = 0.0199 g. Cd).

It has been found that acidic or even neutral cadmium nitrate solution produces no change at all with gallic acid and sodium acetate. This behaviour of cadmium nitrate solution renders its separation from bismuth, lead and copper possible.

The non-appearance of precipitate in the case of cadmium suggests its extreme solubility in acetic acid,

Action of β -Resorcylic Acid on Mercuric Nitrate Solution.

(1 c. c. = 0.02109 g. Hg).

Gallic acid, under the conditions, for the complete precipitation of bismuth, produces with mercuric nitrate solution, an orange precipitate, in the cold, which, on warming, becomes dirty-brown. Thus separation of mercury from lead, copper and cadmium may be possible but not from bismuth. It has, however, been found that using resorcylic acid instead of gallic acid, mercury can be quantitatively precipitated leaving bismuth, lead, copper and cadmium in solution. Thus the separation of mercury from these metals is possible. After separating mercury, the separation of bismuth, lead, etc., can be carried on as stated before.

Resorcylic acid in a faintly acid (nitric) solution of mercuric nitrate, produces a flocculent white precipitate; this, on warming, becomes granular having a faint yellowish tinge, and settles quickly. The precipitate is soluble in dilute mineral and glacial acetic acids, but insoluble in cold or hot water. In precipitating mercury completely from a solution of its nitrate, a solution of β -resorcylic acid saturated in the cold is used in excess (at least 2 c. c. of the solution is required for 0.02 g. of mercury). The solution should not contain more than $N/100$ free acidity (nitric) and for each 0.1g. mercury, the volume should not be less than 40 c. c.

From the above experimental facts, the separation of the metals of 2A analytical group can be easily carried out. The possibility of adsorption of other substances by the precipitates does not materially affect their qualitative separation and detection. However, adjusting the acidity of the wash liquids for the respective precipitates, the adsorption, if any, can be completely avoided.

From the study of the action of the phenolic acids on solutions of lead and copper nitrates, it is found that their separation by any one of the acids is not possible. On dissolving the lead-copper precipitate in a minimum quantity of dilute nitric acid and adding hydrogen peroxide and an excess ammonia and then on boiling, or simply boiling the precipitate with hydrogen peroxide and an excess of ammonia, lead can be precipitated and separated from copper as a yellow or an orange-yellow higher oxide of the type $Pb_xO_y \cdot zH_2O$, where $y > x$.

The procedure of separation of the 2A group metals (a) when required to be precipitated as sulphides, or (b) when all of them are present in nitric acid solution, is shown in a tabular form.

(a) The precipitated sulphides of Hg, Bi, Pb, Cu and Cd are digested (in a basin) with dilute nitric acid (6*N*) and then filtered and washed with cold water.

N.B.—When lead is absent, then the nitrate solution can be neutralised by NH_4OH instead of NaOH .

(b) The nitric acid solution of Hg, Bi, Pb, Cu and Cd is almost neutralised cautiously with NaOH solution, till faintly acidic; boil and add excess of β -resorcylic acid solution with stirring to complete precipitation. Filter and wash once or twice with warm water.

N.B.—In the above separation always fresh solutions of the phenolic acids should be used.

